

An Analysis of Students' Academic Performance in School – Based Assessment and Certificate Examinations in General Mathematics, Physics and Computer Science in Ondo state, Nigeria

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Abstract:

In education, the phrase assessment refers to the wide range of methods and tools that educators use to assess, measure, and document students' academic readiness, learning progress, skill development, and educational needs. There are mainly two methods of assessment in Nigerian schools; viz: School-Based Assessment (SBA) and external examinations. The purpose of this research is to see if SBA has an impact on the final examination grades in secondary schools Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in Ondo State, Nigeria. The researchers employed an ex-post-facto study design to accomplish this. This study used the results of students who took the West African Senior School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) in the 2019/2020 academic year. As a result, the study's population comprised all 2,674 Senior Secondary School students who graduated from all the public senior secondary schools in Akoko South West Local Government Area of Ondo State during the 2019/2020 academic year. The instrument for data collection was the profoma tagged "Instrument of Comparative Performance in School – Based Assessment and External Examination (ICSPSBAEE)". The study's sample comprised 150 students who were chosen at random and in clusters for the study.

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Three research questions and three research hypotheses guided the study overall. The research questions were addressed using descriptive statistic such as mean and standard deviation, and the hypotheses were tested using SPSS version 20's One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at the 0.05 alpha level. The study's findings revealed among others; that students in the researched area of Ondo State performed well in both SBA and external examinations in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics assessments. In all the subjects under investigation, the results revealed a statistically significant difference in the scores of the three types of Assessments. Following the findings, it was suggested that SBA be promoted and made mandatory in all secondary schools; that school administrators ensure that mathematics, Computer Science and Physics syllabi are thoroughly covered; using WAEC and NECO/SSCE as benchmarks, and that Performance in School-Based Evaluation is included in the grading and assessment framework of external exterminations.

Keywords: Comparative Analysis, Academic Performance, School – Based Assessment, Certificate Examinations, Computer Science,

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Introduction

Basic and Post-Basic Education, as well as Career Development are part of Nigerian secondary school education (the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). Three (3) years of Junior Secondary School, known as Basic Education, and three (3) years of Senior Secondary School, known as Post-Basic Education and Career Development, make up this level of education. While Basic Education is the sort of education a child receives immediately following primary school, Post-Basic Education is the type of education a child receives after passing the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE). Students are specifically prepared for the principal aim of secondary education, which is to progress to tertiary education after passing the West African School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) or the National Examination Council (NECO) as the case may be, at Post-Basic Education. As a result, an assessment is one of the most reliable instruments for identifying who advances from one level of school to the next, which is one of the reasons why assessment is seen as such an important component of secondary education in Nigeria.

Assessment in education, according to Odinko (2014), is the systematic process of capturing and analyzing empirical data on knowledge, skill, attitudes, and beliefs in order to evaluate programs and enhance students' learning. Assessment, according to Perry (2013), is the process of determining the importance, significance, or worth of teaching and learning. Assessment data can be derived directly from analyzing students' work to assess learning outcomes, or it can be based on other data from which learning inferences can be drawn. Odinko (2014) also defined assessment as the process of monitoring, recording, and documenting what students do and how they do it in order to take a variety of educational decisions that will have an impact on the student. As a result, assessment refers to the process of converting measuring data into understandable formats to facilitate decision-making. Assessment is therefore an important part of school instruction since it helps teachers identify whether or not students are meeting their educational goals. The assessment also has an impact on grading, placement, progression, instructional needs, curriculum, and, in some cases, funding. Many countries have adopted two major levels of assessment, namely School-Based Evaluation and certificate examinations, in recognition of the importance of assessment in the educational system.

School-Based Assessment is comprehensive, systematic, continuous, diagnostic, and integrative, as guided by the instructor, in addition to the preceding features. This evaluation technique evolved from a classroom setting that required active participation and involvement from students, with a focus on learning rather than grades and scores (Aduloju 2016). School-Based Assessment entails assessing students on a regular basis in the three domains of learning (cognitive, affective, and psychomotor) using a variety of tools such as tests, assignments, observations, interviews, questionnaires, and projects.

Certificate examinations are the second type of assessment. This form of assessment is used to issue a certificate that indicates an examinee's mastery level. The Certificate / external examination is a type of examination that is conducted by professionals outside of the examinee's school, college, or university. Certificate examinations are assessments that are arranged and given by organizations outside the examinee's institution. Because it is external and produces a summative rating of candidates, individual schools have no control over it (Tarnum et al, 2016).

External examinations are conducted in modern Nigeria by indigenous examination bodies such as the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), which administers the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), and the National Examination Council (NECO), which is in charge of administering the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). The National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB), administers the National Technical Certificate (NTC) and National Business Certificate (NBC) examinations, and the Joint Admission Matriculation Board (JAMB), which administers the Universities Matriculation Examinations (UME), are two other external examination bodies in the country. The focus of this research is solely on the WASSCE and NECO examinations, which are administered at the end of the secondary school year.

The analysis of student's performance in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) May/June results in Nigeria from 2007 to 2016 revealed both poor enrolment and performance as shown below:

Table 1: Candidates' Enrolment and Performance in WASSCE in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics between 2007 and 2016

Year	MATHEMATICS			COMPUTER SCIENCE			PHYSICS		
	TOTAL SAT	Credit Passed (A1 - C6)	%	TOTAL SAT	Credit Passed (A1 - C6)	%	TOTAL SAT	Credit Passed (A1 - C6)	%
2007	1,238,163	413,211	33.37	424,747	196,063	46.16	409,449	180,797	44.16
2008	1,259,964	427,644	33.94	456,980	202,762	44.37	408,237	200,345	49.08
2009	1,259,964	453,928	33.87	456,980	203,365	43.49	444,236	222,722	50.14
2010	1,300,418	427,644	32.88	465,643	263,059	50.70	463,755	237,756	51.27
2011	1,505,199	579,432	38.50	565,692	280,250	49.54	563,161	360,096	63.94
2012	1,646,150	587,044	35.66	627,302	270,570	43.13	624,658	429,415	68.74
2013	1,648,363	852,717	51.73	639,296	462,517	72.34	637,023	297,988	46.77
2014	1,365,384	766,971	56.17	636,268	397,649	62.49	635,729	386,270	60.76
2015	1,390,234	798,246	57.42	680,357	412,323	60.60	684,124	410,543	60.01
2016	1,200,367	740,345	61.68	706,873	408,122	57.74	705,125	415,655	58.95

Source: Statistics Section of the WAEC Office Yaba, Lagos (2017).

However, an analysis of candidates' performance in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics and in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) May/June results in Ondo State from 2015 to 2019 revealed that there was no specific pattern in students' performance in the three science subjects under investigation, and the trend in performance did not follow any pattern. Table 2 shows the enrolment and performance of Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in WASSCE in Ondo State from 2015 to 2019.

Table 2: Candidates' Enrolment and Performance in WASSCE in English Language and Computer Science: 2015-2019.

YEAR	Subject	No. Reg.	A1 - C6 (%)	D7 - F9 (%)
2014/15	Mathematics	6691	3974 (59.4)	2117 (40.6)
	Computer Science	6072	4580 (75.4)	1492 (24.6)
	Physics	6069	2863 (47.2)	3206 (52.8)
2015/16	Mathematics	6022	4730 (78.5)	1292 (21.5)
	Computer Science	5189	4403(84.9)	786 (15.1)
	Physics	5231	4173 (79.8)	1048 (20.2)
2016/17	Mathematics	5641	4453 (78.9)	1188 (21.1)
	Computer Science	5258	4894 (93.1)	364 (6.9)
	Physics	5250	2724 (51.9)	2526 (48.1)
2017/18	Mathematics	5578	4637 (83.1)	941 (16.9)
	Computer Science	5155	3964 (76.9)	1191 (23.1)
	Physics	4989	4322 (86.6)	667 (13.4)
2018/19	Mathematics	5563	3922 (70.5)	1641 (29.5)
	Computer Science	5034	3878 (76.9)	1161 (23.1)
	Physics	5014	3386 (67.5)	1628 (32.5)

Source: Statistics Section of the WAEC Office Yaba, Lagos (2020).

Statement of the Problem

School-Based Assessment (SBA) and external examinations have been the two modalities of assessment of students' performance in secondary schools in Nigeria's educational system. Odinko (2014), Asuru (2017), Grina (2012), and Anthony (2018) have all demonstrated the pros and disadvantages of each of these assessment approaches. It is also advised that a student's School-Based Assessment scores in any subject mirror his or her performance on external tests.

Obviously, some researchers, such as Opara, Onyekuru, and Njoku (2015), looked into School-Based Assessment scores as predictors of students' final grades in Rivers and Delta states, respectively, and discovered that School-Based Assessment scores predicted students' performances in JSSCE Physics and integrated science. Tarnum, Obinne, and Achulogy (2016) conducted a comparative analysis of students' mean performance in School-Based

Assessment and certificate exams in Benue state and found that the students did well in both School-Based Assessment and external examinations as evidenced in WASSCE and NECO. Other studies have discovered that students' School-Based Assessment scores are much higher than their certificate test scores.

Most studies in this area, to the best of this researchers' knowledge, were conducted in other regions of the country and have not been conducted in secondary schools in Ondo State in recent times. Furthermore, these scholars were not interested in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics. In the light of the preceding, a more critical investigation with more current data is required to obtain current empirical facts on the mean performance of students in Ondo state secondary schools in School-Based Assessment and external examinations in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics. As a result, the researchers decided to conduct an analysis of students' performance in School-Based Assessments and certificate examinations in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics at senior secondary schools in Ondo State to see if there is a difference in students' mean performance in 2018/2019 School-Based Assessments and external examinations (WAEC and NECO).

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the mean students' scores in Mathematics School-Based Assessments and external examinations?
2. What are the mean students' scores on school-based assessments and external computer science examinations?
3. What are the mean students' scores in Physics School-Based Assessment and external examinations?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were developed and evaluated at the 0.05 significance level.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Mathematics.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Computer Science.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Physics.

Literature Review

The term assessment is used in education to describe the vast range of methods and resources that educators employ to evaluate, measure, and document students' academic preparedness, learning progress, skill acquisition, and educational needs. It is the methodical foundation for drawing conclusions regarding a student's learning and development. The process of defining, developing, choosing, collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and applying the information to improve student's learning and development is referred to as assessment. Hence assessment, on the other hand, is a means to an end rather than an end in itself. Assessment is used for a variety of reasons, including decision-making at the primary,

secondary, and tertiary levels (Ijaya, 2002). Assessment is the methodical gathering of data that provides information about an individual (Okwudire, 2005). There are various degrees of student evaluation. For example, Folajogun (2012) divided assessments into three categories, viz: school-based, public examinations, and international evaluations. Class teachers conduct School-Based Assessments (SBA) in the classroom. School-Based Assessment/ Evaluation, according to Omole & Akawu (2013), is a continuous assessment that takes place on the school grounds under the full supervision of the teacher. It is the evaluation that is planned, managed, and administered by a school's teachers. Classwork, assignments, weekly and monthly tests, field trip reports, laboratory experiment reports, and terminal and annual examinations are all part of this type of assessment.

The external or certificate examination is a type of evaluation that is done with the goal of issuing an external certificate showing the examinee's degree of mastery. (www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary) An external examination is one that is organized by someone outside of a student's own school, college, or university. The external examination is a type of evaluation that is organized and delivered outside of the institution. They are independent of school control and produce summative candidates' evaluations. The primary difference between School-Based Assessment and External Examination therefore, is that the former is prepared, administered, and interpreted by students' teachers, whilst the latter is not under their direct supervision. Regardless of the differences, it is expected that the scores earned by students in School-Based Assessment will match the scores acquired by the same candidates in External Examination in the same disciplines. If this assumption is correct, the following question may arise: are candidates' scores in external examinations the same as in school-based assessments? In Nigeria, certification assessment is external at the primary and secondary school levels, but it is school-based at the tertiary level, although it is regulated by sister institutions.

External examinations began in Nigeria with the introduction of western education. Students were certified after completing each school level of instruction through competency assessments (Adejoh & Obinne, 2013). This resulted in the first school leaving external (FSLC) for primary school leavers and external examinations for secondary school leavers conducted by select external entities. Cambridge University, London University, City and Guilds of London; Royal Society of Arts; and Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), organized some of the external examinations. At the regional and national levels, indigenous examination bodies gradually emerged. The West African Examinations Council (WAEC) administers the West African Senior School External Examination (WASSCE), and the National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) administers the National Technical Certificate (NTC) and National Business Certificate (NBC) examinations, as well as the advanced level versions in the following trades/disciplines. Other bodies include the National Examinations Council (NECO), which oversees the administration of Senior School External Examinations, as well as General Education, Business Trades, Engineering/Construction Trades, and Miscellaneous Trades (<http://www.nabtebnigeria.org/nabteb-in-brief/>) (SSCE). All of these Senior Secondary

School External examinations are taken at the end of the Senior Secondary School educational programme, hence they are not school-based, but rather conducted outside.

The majority of Continuous Assessment studies are either correlational, comparative, or predictive in nature. Ukwuije (2013), for example, employed the Pearson Product Correlation Coefficient to determine the predictive strength of JAMB scores, SCE outcomes, and periodic assessment scores on students' end-of-semester performance. Periodic evaluation scores had the strongest predictive power of the factors studied, according to the study. The data revealed that periodic evaluation procedures are very efficient gauges of academic achievement; certificate worth and outcomes of entry examinations were not significantly connected to end-of-semester performance.

Ibe (2012) looked at the relationship between JAMB exam outcomes and first-year university exam results. According to the findings, JAMB scores in Physics, Chemistry, and Economics were highly connected with university marks in the same courses, however, JAMB scores in Computer Science and Geography were not. Hassan and Adeyanju (2018) investigated the predictive validity of SSCE performance in 13 secondary schools in Nigeria. The majority of Secondary Schools exhibited no significant association between Continuous Assessment scores in English and Basic Science, according to the study. There was, however, a substantial link between student gender and the predictive validity of interview test scores for university admission. In Agricultural Science, Computer Science, English Language, and Geography, interview test scores are predictive indicators for Bachelor's degree accomplishment, however, in Basic Science, there was no significant link between interview test scores and Bachelor's degree achievement. Aliyu and Ngadda (2000) used the College of Education, Gashua as a case study to investigate the relationship between formative and summative evaluation scores. The study also discovered that the formative and summative evaluations of the subjects studied have a substantial positive link. The findings backed up the claim that formative evaluation scores are effective predictors of end-of-semester exam marks. In Rivers and Delta states, respectively, Opara, Onyekuru, and Njoku (2015) investigated School-Based Assessment scores as predictors of students' final grades and discovered that School-Based Assessment scores predicted students' outcomes in JSSCE Physics and integrated science. Tarnum, Obinne, and Achulogy (2016) compared students' mean performance in School-Based Assessment and certificate exams in Benue state and discovered that students performed well in both School-Based Assessment and external tests, as demonstrated by WASSCE and NECO results.

According to the research examined, School-Based Assessment is used in practically all Nigerian schools. This means that the current study follows the standard procedures in all schools. According to the literature, the teacher is the primary implementer of School-Based Assessment, which is also supported by this research. Almost all of the literature reviewed by the researchers is correlative, predictive, or comparative, whereas this study is experimental, making it unique and significant. Some studies have found a positive association between exam scores, while others have found a negative correlation. As a result, the goal of this study

is to see if School-Based Assessments have an impact on final exam marks in Mathematics, computer science and Physics in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was used in this study. This is because it was designed to look into the academic accomplishment of students in Ondo State in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics. The study's population was all the 2,674 Senior Secondary School students who graduated during the 2019/2020 academic year from all public senior secondary schools in Akoko South West Local Government Area of Ondo State. One hundred and fifty (150) students were chosen for the study from five (5) public senior secondary schools in Akoko South West Local Government Area of Ondo State. The five schools were chosen using a cluster selection technique, while the 150 subjects for the study were drawn using a simple random sampling technique. Each of the five public secondary schools had thirty (30) pupils sampled. A proforma named "Instrument of Comparative Students' Performance in School-Based Assessment and External Examination (ICSPSBAEE)"; was used to collect data. The instrument was developed by the researchers and was used to collect data on the performance (scores/grades) of selected candidates in the listed subjects (Mathematics, Computer Studies and Physics) of their annual results while in Senior Secondary School II (SSII) during the 2018/2019 session; in order to create School-Based Assessment scores. The same instrument was used to collect data on the same students' performance in the listed subjects in WASSCE (WAEC) and SSCE (NECO). Students' WASSCE and SSCE (NECO) grades were converted to raw scores as shown in the table below:

Table 3: WASSCE and SSCE (NECO) Scores and their weights

A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	F9
7.0	6.0	5.0	4.0	3.0	2.0	1.0	0.0

WASSCE and SSCE (NECO) are standardized examinations that are guaranteed to be valid and reliable, and so their results, which are categorized as secondary data, are valid and reliable. As a result, the data for this study came from SBA results and examinations conducted by External Examination Bodies. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20 using the descriptive and inferential statistic. The research questions were specifically answered using mean and standard deviation. Because the pass standard is 45 and above, any mean obtained equal to or greater than 45.0 was deemed a satisfactory performance, while any mean received below 45.0 was considered poor. At the 0.05 level of significance, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to see if there was any significant difference between the students' performances in School-Based Assessments and external examinations.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What are the mean students' scores in Mathematics School-Based Assessments and external examinations?

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of performance of students in Mathematics

Subject Area	Exam Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mathematics	WAEC	150	61.14	6.90
	NECO	150	53.28	5.71
	SBA	150	57.09	9.79

The mean scores of students in the School-Based Assessment, WAEC, and NECO in Mathematics are shown in Table 4. It should be emphasized that the average scores on all three exams (SBA, WAEC, and NECO) was greater than 45.0. This demonstrates that students in the investigated area did well in Mathematics in SBA and external assessments. Even though WAEC had the highest performance, the results suggest that SBA (9.79) had the highest variability of scores, followed by WAEC (6.90), and NECO had the lowest variability of scores (5.71). This implied that the scores with the best spread was SBA, followed by WAEC and lastly by NECO.

Research Question 2: What are the mean students' scores on school-based assessments and external computer science examinations?

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of performance of students in Computer Sci

Subject Area	Exam Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Computer Science	WAEC	150	58.31	9.17
	NECO	150	55.79	5.38
	SBA	150	69.81	11.27

The study's findings, as shown in Table 5, show that students in Computer Science performed well on the mean in SBA, WAEC, and NECO. It should be emphasized that the mean scores for all three forms of assessment were above 45.0. This demonstrates that students in the study area in Ondo State did well in Computer Science in all three exams. SBA had the highest score variation (11.27), followed by WAEC (9.17), while NECO had the lowest (5.38). This implied that the scores of the SBA also had the best spread, followed by WAEC and then by NECO.

Research Question 3: What are the mean students' scores on school-based assessments and external physics examinations?

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of performance of students in Physics

Subject Area	Exam Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Physics	WAEC	150	48.27	7.62
	NECO	150	58.19	7.38
	SBA	150	49.43	13.22

The outcome from Table 6 displays the mean scores of students in physics across the School-Based Assessment, WAEC, and NECO. It should be emphasized that the average scores for all three exams (SBA, WAEC, and NECO) exceeded the benchmark of 45.0. This suggests that students in the researched area did well on the three exams in Physics. Students' scores varied the most in SBA (13.22) and NECO (7.38) while WAEC had the least variation (7.62) in Physics scores. This suggested that the SBA scores continued to have the best spread.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Mathematics.

To test this null hypothesis, the One-Way between-groups Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to see if there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Mathematics.

Table 7: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of scores of students in Mathematics

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Group	241.378	2	120.689	53.937	.000
Within Group	5425.400	148	30.652		
Total	5666.778	150			

p>0.05

The result in table 7 indicated that there was a statistically significant difference at the $p < 0.05$ in the scores of the three modes of Assessments: $F=53.937$, $P= .000$. Hence, the null hypothesis was not upheld.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Computer Science.

To test this null hypothesis, the One-Way between-groups analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to see if there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Computer Science.

Table 8: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of scores of students in Computer Science

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Group	28421.228	2	14244.328	97.251	.000
Within Group	71554.237	148	95.338		
Total	99975.465	150			

p>0.05

The result in table 8 indicated that there was a statistically significant difference at the $p < 0.05$ in the scores of the three modes of Assessments: $F=97.251$, $P= .000$. Hence, the null hypothesis was not upheld.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Physics.

To test this null hypothesis, the One-Way between-groups Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to explore whether there was no significant difference between the mean scores of students in School-Based Assessment and External Examinations in Physics.

Table 9: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of scores of students in Physics

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Group	1608.133	2	3217.227	63.482	.000
Within Group	2486.417	148	49.185		
Total	4094.550	150			

p>0.05

The result in table 9 indicated that there was a statistically significant difference at the $p < 0.05$ in the scores of the three modes of Assessments: $F=63.482$, $P= .000$. Hence, the null hypothesis was not upheld.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings revealed that students in the investigated area fared well in both SBA and external Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics assessments. This finding is in contrast to Gani & Attah (2013), who claimed that teachers do not adhere to the qualities of

SBA, preventing it from being comparable to external assessments. They claimed that teachers merely utilize SBA to help pupils prepare for external examinations. If the mean external examination performance and SBA performance are both above the benchmark, it indicates that teachers in the investigated area are effectively using SBA to monitor teaching and learning. Despite the fact that the students did well in all of the examinations, the research revealed that the SBA had a consistently higher variability of marks than the external exams. This is in line with Monday, Ikiroma, and Nwogwugwu (2014), who believe that class teachers are the best people to judge whether or not students have mastered the content. This study's findings are similar to those of Opara, Onyekuru, and Njoku(2015), who discovered that students' performance in Physics and Integrated Science was predicted by School-Based Assessment scores.

In a similar vein, Tarnum, Obinne, and Achulogy (2016) discovered that students performed well in both School-Based Assessments and external examinations, as shown by WASSCE and NECO results. This could also be explained by the fact that the external examination results were the midpoints of the grade ranges achieved by the sampled students. This could explain the limited variability in the score spread that was observed. The students investigated in the three Examinations performed better than the benchmark of 45.0 in Computer Science. This demonstrated that the students did well in the SBA, WASSCE, and NECO/SSCE examinations. This was in contrast to Nworgu's (1992) assertion that teacher-made test items are of poor quality and that SBA is merely used to prepare pupils for WASSCE and NECO/SSCE. If the teacher-made materials were not up to par, as Nworgu (1992) claimed, it would have had a negative impact on the students' performance. The study also discovered that in the three examinations (WASSCE, NECO / SSCE, and SBA) in the area of Ondo State under inquiry, there was a statistically significant variation in the mean scores of students in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics.

Conclusion

The study has been able to establish the comparison between students' academic performances in School-Based Assessment and External Examination in SSCE examination in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study concluded that the mean scores of students in Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in the three tests (WASSCE, NECO / SSCE, and SBA) in Ondo State were statistically significant. Secondary schools in the area also performed well in both school-based and external assessments. Through School-Based Assessment, the students are adequately prepared for their External Examinations.

Recommendations

The recommendations hereunder are provided based on the findings of this study:

1. The academic standards set by state teachers to achieve high academic standards should be maintained.

2. Performance in School-Based Evaluation should be included in the grading and assessment framework of external examinations, as is frequently recognized in policy documents.
3. Students should be given extensive opportunities to study past external examination questions while still in school so that they are familiar with them.
4. Teachers should receive extensive training in the methods for designing, conducting, and interpreting school-based examinations that meet the same standards as external examinations.
5. Government should provide educational facilities and learning materials, particularly laboratory equipment, to suit the demands of students studying computer science and Physics theory and practical exercises.
6. Teachers' abilities and methodologies should be improved in order to increase Mathematics, computer science and Physics learning in schools.
7. School administrators should guarantee that Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics syllabi are thoroughly covered, using WAEC and NECO SSCE as benchmarks, with proper encouragement and monitoring of teachers.
8. School-Based Assessment should be promoted and made mandatory in all secondary schools, particularly in core disciplines such as English and Mathematics.
9. Teachers should make efforts to conduct regular school-based assessments for students, right from JSS 1.

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